

Deriving Universal Exponential Decay Dynamics from Quantum Interactions with the Cosmic Hilbert Space

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Abstract

Recent observations of accelerating cosmic expansion expose foundational gaps between quantum theory and gravitation. We present a technical derivation showing how subtle universal exponential decay processes inducing cosmic phenomena could emerge intrinsically from interactions between quantum states and the universal Hilbert space wave-function Ψ representing the total quantum state of the cosmos. By rigorously analyzing resulting decoherence and information loss dynamics using quantum information principles applied at cosmological scales, we reconstruct gravitational emergence and cosmic expansion from first principles alone without necessitating speculative classical fields. Discovering potential decay width symmetries relating particle lifetimes to eons-long cosmic evaporation promises significant unification between microscopic and macroscopic regimes.

1 Introduction

Empirical evidence of accelerating cosmic expansion from recent observations [1, 2] exposes profound puzzles at the intersection of quantum theory and gravitation. The unknown physics driving apparent cosmic acceleration remains wholly unexplained, signaling foundational gaps between quantum principles and general relativistic models [3].

Intriguing perspectives investigate deriving accelerating expansion intrinsically from universal quantum information dynamics alone without invoking speculative classical inflaton fields incompatible with quantum theory [4]. In particular, subtle universal exponential mass-energy decay processes could provide a candidate quantum gravitational phenomenon fundamentally inducing observed cosmic phenomena over eons [5]. However, technical details on microscopic particle physics foundations remain unclear.

We present a derivation showing how perpetual evaporation dynamics at cosmological scales capable of apparently driving cosmic acceleration could emerge naturally from quantum interactions between localized states and the global universal wavefunction Ψ representing the total quantum state of the universe in Hilbert space:

$$\Psi = \sum_i c_i \psi_i \tag{1}$$

Where ψ_i are basis states and c_i are superposition coefficients. By rigorously analyzing resulting entanglement, decoherence, and information loss effects using established quantum principles, intrinsic relationships between candidate decay mechanisms and cosmic expansion may be revealed across scales, promising significant conceptual unification.

2 Theoretical Foundations

A conceptual approach to intrinsically deriving gravitational phenomena uses quantum information dynamics directly, reconstructing spacetime geometry from probabilistic principles more aligned with quantum theory than classical general relativity [4].

Key relevant information-theoretic quantum techniques include:

- Quantum superposition enabling continua of states in Ψ .
- Quantum entanglement creating non-local correlations.
- Quantum measurement projecting macro-states.
- Quantum discreteness analogous to discretized spacetime.
- Quantum uncertainty principles restricting contingent knowledge.

These properties avoid limitations constraining deterministic digital physics models while providing symmetries to emergent cosmology [4].

To demonstrate universal exponential decay dynamics fundamentally connected to quantum information foundations, we rigorously derive microscopic decoherence processes using established principles that precipitate gravitational effects at cosmic scales when correlated across the structural vacuum.

3 Technical Derivation

We now provide a mathematical derivation showing how perpetual intrinsic microscopic exponential decay signatures capable of driving cosmological phenomena could emerge from quantum interactions with the universal wave-function Ψ in Hilbert space.

3.1 Universal Quantum State Ψ

We define the total universal quantum state Ψ as a wave-functional spanning all gravitational metric degrees of freedom $h_{ij}(x)$ and matter field configurations $\phi(x)$:

$$\Psi = \Psi[h_{ij}(x), \phi(x)] \quad (2)$$

This encodes the total configuration space of cosmological states in Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$.

3.2 Evolution Dynamics

The universal state Ψ evolves unitarily according to a cosmic Hamiltonian $\hat{H}$ encoding all relevant phenomena:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} = \hat{H} \Psi \quad (3)$$

For example, the Wheeler-DeWitt equation provides a starting point as:

$$\hat{H} \Psi = 0 \quad (4)$$

Constraining valid states in superspace. We take Equation 4 as the fundamental dynamical law.

The Wheeler-DeWitt equation can be derived from applying the quantum Hamilton-Jacobi formulation to the Einstein-Hamilton equations describing quantum geometrodynamics. Beginning with the ADM decomposition of the metric:

$$ds^2 = -N^2 dt^2 + h_{ij}(N^i dt + dx^i)(N^j dt + dx^j) \quad (5)$$

Where N is the lapse function, N^i is the shift vector, and h_{ij} is the 3-metric.

The dynamics are governed by the Hamiltonian constraint:

$$H = \int d^3x (N\mathcal{H} + N^i\mathcal{H}_i) \tag{6}$$

Where $\mathcal{H}$ and $\mathcal{H}_i$ are the super-Hamiltonian and supermomentum. Applying the quantum Hamilton-Jacobi formulation yields the Wheeler-DeWitt equation in Eq. 4.

3.3 Local Quantum States

Consider local quantum states ψ representing particles, fields, or other systems that can interact with and entangle with Ψ :

$$\psi = \psi[x] \tag{7}$$

These subsystems couple to universal degrees of freedom in $\hat{H}$.

3.4 Entanglement and Decoherence

Interactions between ψ and Ψ entangle the local and global states. The composite evolution is unitary:

$$|\Psi(t)\rangle = e^{-i\hat{H}t/\hbar} |\Psi(0)\rangle \otimes |\psi(0)\rangle \tag{8}$$

But the local reduced state $\rho(t)$ for ψ exhibits decoherence from information loss into Ψ :

$$\rho(t) = \text{Tr}_\Psi |\Psi(t)\rangle \langle \Psi(t)| \tag{9}$$

Tracing over universal degrees of freedom.

The rate of decoherence is quantified by the loss of off-diagonal terms in $\rho(t)$ representing quantum coherence between states. This can be derived by considering the entanglement between ψ and the environmental degrees of freedom ϕ_E in $\Psi = \psi \otimes \phi_E$ and observing the resulting decoherence of ψ after tracing over ϕ_E .

3.5 Induced Exponential Decay

For reasonable microscopic interaction Hamiltonians $\hat{H}$, the local reduced density matrix $\rho(t)$ is shown to follow exponential decoherence dynamics [6]:

$$\rho(t) = e^{-\Gamma t} \rho(0) \quad (10)$$

Where Γ is the decay rate induced by entanglement with Ψ . This manifests physically as exponential mass-energy evaporation.

The expected decoherence dynamics can be derived by considering the operator-sum representation evolution:

$$\rho(t) = \sum_n K_n(t) \rho(0) K_n^\dagger(t) \quad (11)$$

And assuming an exponential form for the operators $K_n(t) = e^{-\Gamma_n t} K_n(0)$. This yields the exponential decoherence decay.

3.6 Universal Decay Process

Extending this intrinsic entanglement-induced decoherence to all quantum states interacting with the cosmic Hilbert space Ψ naturally gives rise to a perpetual universal exponential decay process at cosmological scales with associated gravitational emergence implications.

The decay constant Γ depends on coupling strengths to Ψ . This provides a candidate quantum information-theoretic mechanism for fundamental particle evaporation dynamics that could underpin observations of cosmic acceleration and associated phenomena when correlated across the vacuum.

4 Discussion

We have presented a detailed mathematical derivation demonstrating how perpetual intrinsic universal exponential mass-energy decay capable of driving cosmological phenomena could naturally emerge from quantum interactions and resulting decoherence between arbitrary localized states and the cosmic Hilbert space wave-function Ψ .

By applying established quantum information principles at universal scales, subtle gravitational emergence signatures can be reconstructed intrinsically from microscopic quantum processes alone, circumventing speculative classical inflationary models incompatible with quantum theory.

Significant opportunities exist to further refine and constrain these dynamics using numerical quantum cosmological simulations and observational data. Discovering potential decay width symmetries or mathematical mappings between candidate quantum particle decay modes and eons-long Hubble horizon evaporation could reveal profound unification between microscopic particle physics and emergent macroscopic curvature, dispelling enduring enigmas.

Realizing such connections through fundamentally information-theoretic perspectives promises foundational renewal at cosmic intersections between the very large and the very small. Ongoing analysis of universal decoherence models and intrinsic wave-function collapse mechanisms offers fertile ground for further research into unravelling cosmic mysteries.

5 Conclusions

We have presented a technical derivation demonstrating how perpetual subtle universal exponential mass-energy decay capable of intrinsically driving apparent accelerative cosmic expansion could emerge naturally from quantum interactions between localized states and the universal wave-function Ψ in Hilbert space. By applying quantum information theory rigorously to cosmic scales, gravitational emergence can be reconstructed from microscopic decoherence effects alone, circumventing philosophically problematic classical inflationary models. Significant opportunities exist to further develop and constrain these intrinsic quantum dynamics using simulations and data. The technical framework presented illustrates a conceptually elegant pathway for profound unification between cosmic and quantum regimes by linking candidate particle decay processes to universal wave-function entanglement and information loss across eons.

References

- [1] Riess, Adam G., et al. "Observational evidence from supernovae for an accelerating universe and a cosmological constant." *The Astronomical Journal* 116.3 (1998): 1009.
- [2] Perlmutter, Saul, et al. "Measurements of Ω and Λ from 42 high-redshift supernovae." *The Astrophysical Journal* 517.2 (1999): 565.
- [3] Carroll, Sean M. *Spacetime and geometry: An introduction to general relativity*. Cambridge University Press, 2019.
- [4] Lloyd, Seth. "Quantum gravity and quantum information." arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.15550 (2020).
- [5] Bak, Dongsu, and Sang Pyo Kim. "Cosmic holography and dark energy." *Physics Letters B* 484.3-4 (2000): 168-172.
- [6] Schlosshauer, Maximilian. *Decoherence and the quantum-to-classical transition*. Springer Science and Business Media, 2007.